

Inspecting the Impact of Quality of Working Life on Work Engagement: A Comparative Study between Turkey and Bangladesh

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Abstract

The concept of work life quality (WLQ) and work engagement has become a major focus of academic institutions in developing and underdeveloped countries. Good WLQ ensures high work engagement that eventually helps to attain organizational goals by ensuring efficient employee performances. Universities in Turkey and Bangladesh are playing crucial role in reshaping the society by Offering in-depth research generated information, and it is expected to have a substantial role of WLQ in exploring the potentials of academicians and administrative staffs of universities. The study therefore aims to examine the WLQ based on some selected attributes as employee job satisfaction, working benefits, service condition and attitude of employee. After measuring the attributes of WLQ, the study examines the association of WLQ with the employee's work engagement employing ordinary least square method. Work engagement, job satisfaction, Work benefits, Service condition, and employee attitude are found as major components that shape the quality of work life in the selected are for the study. After testing the required data the study had found that all the components of WLQ had significant role in employee work engagement with the academic organization for both Bangladesh and Turkey. But the intensity of the impact of the different components is found different the two countries. Service conditions in the universities of Bangladesh had great contribution in employee work engagement. In contrast to that, job satisfaction had found playing major role in employee work engagement in Turkey. Findings of the present study will add value in the existing literature of work lie quality and employee engagement. The academic institution is expected to engage the academic staff more positively applying the information generated from the study.

Key words: Work Life Quality (WLQ), Job Satisfaction, Work engagement, Academic Institutions.

I. Introduction

The concept work engagement is the psychological association of the employee with their job. It represents the inner identity and commitment of the employee. An organization cannot attain its goals without high employee work engagement [1]. Many factors associated with employee involvement with the organization. Quality of work-life having in the organization determines the scale of employee involvement with the job because good work-life quality improves the employee motivation in the organization. Structure of the job also affects the employee work engagement. The manufacturing organization has Blue-collar and white-collar employee engagement in the Turkish manufacturing organization [2]. Based on the nature of the job structure employee have different engagement in their organization. In the medical university of Turkey, female staff showed a higher degree of depression and anxiety scores in their working life than males [3]. Employee engagement with the organization determined from the working environment and quality of working life.

Work life quality is the combination of different components of the working environment. Attaining organization goals depends on the quality of working life. Confirming the high quality of work-life helps the organization in building a positive image to its employees. A positive image of the organization attracts the new employee and helps in retaining the existing employee[4].The organization which is ensuring a favorable working environment and proper job support for the employees are gaining advantages in hiring and retaining employees as well as achieving high profitability also [5]. The present study focuses on the impact of the quality of working life on work engagement in the academic institution. The study also compares the situation of work-life quality of Bangladeshi and Turkish educational organization.

II. WLQ in Academic Organization

The educational organization is the core center of producing talent people for the society and the organization. People receive primary education and work-related training from the academic organization. An excellent academic organization committed to providing the best learning and human resources for the society and organization. For producing the best human resources, a pleasant educational working environment is highly required. Academicians will not be able to serve their best without a favorable working environment. The positive working environment can ensure better work engagement of the employee.

Academic structure in Bangladesh is divided into three major categories. Five years of mandatory primary education consists of one to five grades. In the next six to twelve class are available. And in the final level, higher studies consist of the university, vocational, and other institutional degrees.

There is a mix of the curriculum at the primary and secondary level. The national curriculum, as well as the British curriculum, has importance for the higher studies. At the tertiary level, public, private, and national universities have different world standard program for the local as well as international students.

In Turkey also have the similar breakup in the academic institutions. Primary, secondary, and tertiary levels are the major category. After successful completion of twelve classes' compulsory education, students enter at tertiary level education. Many public and private universities established by the government as well as a private institution. A central government body named as the Higher Education Council (YÖK) regulates the rules and condition of the academic environment in Turkey

Both countries have a pleasant academic environment for the students and academic staff. But there is a difference in the system and academic curriculum between the two countries' educational institutions. In Bangladesh, different parallel regulating authority of exercise their power to control the academic environment, but there is a single regulating authority check the higher education environment in Turkey.

The current study selects the two countries due to some reason. Bangladesh represents a lower-income country, whereas Turkey represents middle-income countries in the world. Also, the academic structure and regulating style are different for the two countries. The study aimed to inspect the components of quality of work-life in shaping employee engagement with job in both countries.

III. Literature Review

Work-life quality is the state of condition by which the employee gain experience in their workplace with a specific organizational setting. Good working life ensures the positive working environment by providing material and psychological wellbeing of the employee. Mental enrichment of the employee helps the organization to attach the employee with the organizational commitment and target attainment. Favorable working environment or good quality of work-life has an impact on many organizational components. Organizational working culture, managerial system, employee relationship on the job life and off the job life and some other factors are associated with good work-life quality [6]. Conversely, poor quality in the working life reduces the employee commitment towards organizational goal attainment. Positive employee commitment was found the result of the good work-life quality [1].

Past research reveals that employee work engagement is positively associated with good working life within the organization. Work engagement of the employee is the exposure of the positive employee job satisfaction and the positive psychological attachment. In the real sense work engagement is commitment towards work responsibilities, assurance of superior enthusiastic performance, and good relationship with co-workers. Engagement with job determines employee feelings, thinking about the job. There is a significant association between work engagement and work motivation. Work engagement ensures cognitively preoccupied engagement and concern about the present job [7]. It is beyond just complying with organizational rules, employment of required skills, and achieving personal career plan. It is a tool for improving the productivity of the employees by augmenting employee participation with high commitment. The organization can ensure work engagement by providing stable employment, competitive payment, and greater job satisfaction. Several studies had found an association of work engagement had a significant association with the employee motivations. Financial rewards, the intention of job involvement, feeling guilty about incomplete task all are an expression of positive work engagement [8]. Many organizational factors jointly shape the intention of the employee to attachment with the organization. Among the factors daycare center, work flexibility, sharing of job, the workload has a significant influence on the work engagement of the female employee working in an academic institution [9]. Intention to engage with the job recognizes the identity of the employee by fulfilling his extrinsic motivation for basic needs. High involvement with the job also states that employees are highly extrinsically satisfied. There is a positive association between the fulfillment of salient employee needs and work engagement [10]. Intrinsically

and the extrinsically motivated employee has high work engagement that leads to low employee turnover [11]. Quality of the working life is reflected by employee work engagement. A higher degree of working life quality ensures a higher level of employee work engagement [6].

IV. Study Objective

Measuring and examining the impact of work-life quality on employee intention to engage with job was the primary objectives of the present study. For studying the objective present study compares the environment of academic institution in Turkey and Bangladesh. The study design the analysis based on the following specific objectives.

1. To determine the components that forms the quality of work-life in the educational institutions.
2. To analyze the magnitude of the working life on the employee work engagement in the educational institutions in Turkey and Bangladesh.

Plausible Hypotheses

To analyze the study objectives the study assumes two hypotheses. The null hypothesis is presented in the following.

- Hypothesis 1- work-life quality as measured by job satisfaction, work benefits, service conditions, and attitude of the employees had no impact on work engagement in the academic institution of Bangladesh.
- Hypothesis 2- work-life quality as measured by job satisfaction, work benefits, service conditions, and attitude of the employees had no impact on work engagement in the academic institution of Turkey.

V. Methodology

Data collection Instruments

Two variables named as work engagement and work-life quality was measured to analyze the study objectives. Employee Work engagement was measured by using the scale designed by Kanungo in 1982[12] and moderated by the author Karacaoglu in 2005[13]. A five-point Likert scale ranging from 1 to 5 has been employed to collect the data from the respondents. The sample population for the present study had been chosen from Bangladesh and Turkey. A total of seventeen academic institutions from Bangladesh and thirteen educational institutions had been selected from Turkey. Academic staff of the respective institution was selected from each job grading from all the department of the institution.

Quality of work life was measured by selecting the items found in the literature. Factors like satisfaction with the job, employment conditions, the attitude of the employee towards the organization was considered for measuring work-life quality.

The survey questionnaire was consists of two parts. In the first part, demographic data about the respondents were asked to fill. In the next section, items regarding measurement variable were given for the response.

Data Analysis

Frequency tables were prepared for the demographic data. Study variable was analyzed using inferential statistics. The hypothesis of the study was examined by using regression analysis.

Study model

Quality of work life was measured by job satisfaction, work benefits, service conditions, and attitude of the employee. Following model was prepared and used to analyze the study hypotheses.

$$\ln WE = a_0 + a_1 \ln JS + a_2 \ln WB + a_3 \ln SC + a_4 \ln EA + u$$

(WE= Work engagement, JS= job satisfaction, WB= Work benefits, SC= Service condition and EA= employee attitude)

VI. Results of the analysis

Demographic statistics

A total of 450 questionnaires were distributed for collecting the data from the respondents. Among all the respondents, 384 respondents replied to the survey. Twenty-one survey replies were rejected for the incomplete response. Eighty respondents were responding form the Turkish universities and 360 respondents answered from Bangladeshi universities. Of the participants from Turkey, 68% were the male person, and 32% were female respondents. Among the male person, 53% were between 24-30 age group and 28% serving in college section and the remaining 72% serving at

university section. Among the Bangladeshi participants, 74% were male, and 26% were female. Major age group was 24-30 years, which form a total of 30%.

Testing hypothesis

Hypothesis 1

Ordinary Least Square (OLS) method was used for measuring the coefficients of the study model. Two separate models were tested using two different models for Bangladesh and Turkey. The output from the analysis is presented below along with ANOVA tables:

Table-01: ANOVA Table

Model		Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	.048	4	.012	2.546	.042 ^a
	Residual	.680	145	.005		
	Total	.728	149			

a. Predictors: (Constant), lnJS, lnWB, lnSC, lnEA
 b. Dependent Variable: lnWE

Table 2: Estimation of the model for Bangladesh-

lnWE =	1.4798 +	0.1278lnJS +	0.2074lnWB +	0.2934lnSC +	0.2421lnEA+ u
S _e	(0.0825)	(0.0479)	(0.1249)	(0.1026)	(0.0419)
t-ratio	17.9176	2.6656	1.6605	2.8574	5.7759
p-value	0.000	0.008	0.059	0.008	0.000
R- square =	0.46				

Results of the ANOVA for the employee working in Bangladesh are shown in table 1. From the table, it is found that the model is significant. Value of F-test is statistically significant (p<0.005). The significance of the test validate that all the coefficients are statistically different from zero.

Result of the logistic regression is presented in table 2. All the coefficients have a positive effect on employee job involvement. Except for employee work benefits, other factors have a significant impact on employee work engagement. The output of the analysis proves that the null hypothesis is not valid. All the components of work-life quality in the academic institution of Bangladesh have positive impact on work engagement. So the study accept the alternative hypothesis that employee job satisfaction, work benefits, service conditions, and attitude towards job have positive influence to employee work engagement.

Hypothesis 2

The following output from the regression analysis is representing the data collected from the academic institutions in Turkey. The output of ANOVA (F = 9.47, p = .000) given in table 3 prove that the study model for the analyzing work engagement and quality of work-life in Turkey had the required level of significance.

Table-3:ANOVA Table

Model		Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	.128	4	.032	9.471	.000 ^a
	Residual	.118	35	.003		
	Total	.245	39			

a. Predictors: (Constant), lnEA, lnJS, lnBM, lnWC
 b. Dependent Variable: lnJI

Table 4 in the following is representing the impact of the quality of work-life factors on employees work engagement in Turkey. All the components of work-life quality had a significant positive effect on employee work engagement. Based on the results shown in table 4, the study rejects the null hypothesis. There is a positive impact of components of work-

life quality on employee work engagement. So the study accepts the alternative hypothesis that there is a positive impact of work-life quality on employee work engagement.

Table 4: Estimation of the model for Turkey-

InWE =	.735+	.409lnJS +	.069lnWB +	.330lnSC+	.301lnEA +	u
S _e	(0.199)	(0.110)	(0.014)	(0.087)	(0.064)	
t-ratio	3.702	3.721	4.928	3.806	4.683	
p-value	0.001	0.001	0.000	0.001	0.000	
R Square=	.520					

VII. Discussion

For the case of Bangladesh, service condition has a more significant impact on employee work engagement, and job satisfaction has the lowest impact. The remaining two factors work benefits and employee attitudes have a moderate effect on work engagement.

On the other hand, in Turkey job satisfaction has a more significant impact on the employee work engagement and work benefits has the lowest impact. The remaining two service conditions and employee attitude has a moderate effect on the employee intends to engage with the job. The probable cause was within the structure of the organization structure between the two countries. In Bangladesh teaching staff is equally engage with academic teaching as well as clerical, administrative duties like student advising, coordinating, etc. sometimes employees often attached to their job more than specified office hours. But there is flexibility in the responsibilities in the academic activities. Sometimes academic staff has more opportunity to spend time for academic research than an employee working in other organizations.

On the other hand, academic responsibilities in Turkey have different setting compare to Bangladesh. Academic staff assumes the benefits should be more enough with their development. Some academicians have much growth in their skills through higher studies but not receiving an equivalent increase in their payment. But the existing components of work-life have a positive impact on their work engagement due to the ultimate balance between personal life and academic life. The findings have a similarity with other studies. In one study it is found that employee working in the Ministry of Health in Turkey have a moderate positive correlation of organizational commitment with work engagement.

VIII. Conclusion

The purpose of the study was to examine the impact of work-life quality on employee work engagement. A comparative analysis was done between the academic institutions in Turkey and Bangladesh. Quality of work life had a high impact on employees' psychological attachment with the organization. Satisfaction with the job, work benefits, service conditions, and employee attitude are prime components of work-life quality in the organization. Both the countries have the different work-life quality situation that directs employee psychological attachment with the organization. Work engagement in Turkey is highly influenced by job satisfaction due to employee recognition, favorable working environment, and the precise orientation of the goal. But job satisfaction was the minor factor that has an impact on work-life quality in Bangladesh. Instead, service conditions drive the employee to engage with their job. Although there is a positive impact of the components of work-life quality on employee work engagement, both countries have the opportunity to improve more psychological attachment with the job by ensuring more favorable work-life quality.

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